

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF FORMING SAVING AND ECONOMIC EDUCATION IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article gives you a brief overview on economics and how to do it right. The scientific and pedagogical bases of austerity education of the younger generation are covered.*

Keywords: *thrift, entrepreneurship, hard work, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship, vocational training, economic accounting, family budget, parenting, new technologies, market laws, honesty, purity, generosity.*

In the **introduction** of the article, the reformation of society based on social and national needs is dependent on high humanitarian ideals. Reconstruction of vocational education requires a completely comprehensive approach to the content, form and methods of the field. It is today's task of the field of pedagogy to find ways to improve the educational process by providing perfection, accuracy, and consistency based on vital requirements.

Such approaches to modern pedagogy and educational models are being developed, which create an opportunity to approach the production-technological process, guaranteeing the achievement of the intended goals.

The idea of educational technology is to increase the effectiveness of the teaching process and ensure that it achieves the planned results under certain conditions. The essence of such an approach to activity is to organize the educational process by dividing it into elements according to details and forming it to the maximum extent.

In the **theoretical aspects** of the article, the research process shows that modern education based on new pedagogical technologies significantly differs from traditional educational foundations, educational methods and tools, forms of its organization and results. In the process of technology education, it is necessary to consider the expediency of using modern educational methods (methods) using new pedagogical technologies in the process of education. The teaching method is a regulated method of organizing the interdependent activities of the learner and the teacher to achieve the goal set in teaching. The technique is one of the important factors that ensure the achievement of a certain result. During this period, students learn to know, master and appreciate one or another skill. At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher's and the student's thinking on a certain issue, according to the rule, are different from each other. Therefore, first of all, the teacher conveys his research discoveries and educational goals to the learner. The developed methodology ensures that the educational content is delivered to the student at the intended level. In this case, the activity of the teacher is the methods of imparting knowledge, and the activity of the learner is the methods of learning.

It is possible to work together only when the goals of the teacher and the learner coincide. Educational goals are based on the joint activity of the teacher and the learner, teaching is carried out with the help of tools, and methods provide their practical expression. Teaching methods (methods) - a means of organizing the teacher's activity, reading methods reflect the organization of the learner's activity. Its task is to study the laws of teaching and to determine the relation of requirements to teachers' activities based on them. In other words, the methodology is

a set of certain methods by which the requirements for teaching are implemented. In the teaching of technology education, it is necessary to distinguish between two situations - theoretical orientation of teaching and teaching methodology.

The teaching methodology should eliminate the pedagogical methods that can convey the theoretical essence of the subject being studied to the student, teaching methods and forms of teaching as teaching methods and education, Didactics, which develops a whole set of content and issues, is a part of the theory of mummy. The methodology is related to the laws of this or that subject being taught and studied.

In the **practical** aspects of the article, the teaching of technology education is conducted on the basis of general methodological requirements. At the same time, teaching each of these subjects requires its own methodology that reflects the content of the subject. Methodology of formation of economic education in the lesson of technology education There are many other classifications in this regard. For example, the German scientist A. Klinberg shows monologue and dialogue methods as forms of cooperation in reading.

Monologue method	Form of cooperation	Dialogue method
Lecture	Individual	Conversations
Story	With a group	
Shows	Frontal with a team	

The process of checking the formation of economic education among students is aimed at solving the following didactic issues:

Determining the quality of knowledge, skills and competencies related to economic efficiency. The quality of knowledge, skills and abilities to economic efficiency is first of all characterized by their thoroughness and awareness. In order to be sure of the thoroughness of knowledge, skills and abilities related to economic savings, it is necessary to check them not only during their acquisition, but also in the further activities of students. Economic education is an important condition for the well-being of a person. Economic education of young people has been and remains one of the problems of pedagogy. The importance of economic education for young people is incomparable in the conditions of transition to the market economy and in the process of further development. In this regard, significant work is being done by our government. Economic thinking covers all stages of a person's life - his personal life, his relationship with people, his behavior. Economic thinking leads a teenager to look at life in a different way, to become familiar with social relations. People develop skills for these situations.

The formation of economic thinking creates new directions in the solution of complicated problems in the economy. Thus, the pedagogical process of economic education in schools should have the following qualitative stages.

- very good knowledge of the state's economic situation;
- to know the economic bases of various property types and enterprises;
- literacy for objective assessment of evidence and analysis of existing economic bases;
- initiative in production and economic affairs, economic relations.

Conditions of economic education require a variety of questions from students. They include:

- dependence of economic education in the family and general secondary education schools, its acceptable distribution;
- the role of didactic principles in students' learning;
- economic education of students by summarizing practical experiences in the process of teaching academic subjects at school and explaining the role of science in the acceleration of scientific and technological development;
- protection of state and private property, electricity, gas, educational literature, equipment, school building, home furnishings and household appliances;
- explaining the economic aspects of economical use of material resources;
- organization of economic education for students outside of school hours;
- to teach general secondary school students economic thinking in order to develop skills about higher education institutions and the conditions after them.

In the formation of new economic thinking, new stages of economic education, ways to further improve the training of personnel in the economic field, can be improved in the following ways:

- organizing the process of performing practical work based on the acquired theoretical knowledge;
- obligations of economic preparation necessary for vocational training and improving the qualification of each student;
- to determine the nature of production and work, the level of knowledge of personnel in the economic sphere;
- the system of acquiring new knowledge in the field of economy, acquiring new information technologies (scientific literature and the Internet).

One of the necessary conditions in the economic education of students is to prepare them for economic activity. This creates opportunities for students to actively participate in economic life. This requires young people to know the basis of the economic interests of our society, to use economic knowledge effectively, to expand production and to use the environment and material resources wisely. Preparation for economic activity includes the following main components:

- economic demand and interest;
- economic general educational preparation;
- formation of economic relations with labor, manufactured products, environment and time.

Economic demands are new forms of material well-being and economic activity that society, social groups, political parties, etc. strive to achieve.

General education economic preparation (system of economic knowledge, knowledge, knowledge and experience) is one of the important components of the system of preparing a person for economic activity. And in personal structures, it relies on experience. The relevance of economic education comes from the conditions of general and polytechnic education. The product developed in this case complies with the principles of legislation and science in society. Thus, economic education is based on the general theoretical condition that the economy should be reworked by several generations. The economic life of the society is rich and multifaceted. It's a science within itself . Transactions in the ordinary course of business include working capital, production, sales, and inventory. The nature and activity of economic life is determined by the production of material goods. All the participants of the society, including the students, even if

they are not producers, participate in the economic life. Conscious participation in economic life and activity requires special training from a person.

Economic education cannot be imagined without a team. To teach children to work, first of all, it is necessary to teach them to work and encourage their work in different ways. It is necessary to teach them to use material resources and manufactured products sparingly, while forming teamwork skills. It is these relationships that indicate the objective collectivization of economic categories as important principles of life, and the usefulness of working with a team.

In conclusion, it can be said that in developed times, especially in independent Uzbekistan, which is rapidly developing, the issue of economic education is approached from the point of view of preserving state property and strengthening it, and this is considered as the first task. This means that for many years economists, pedagogues, philosophers and technologists have a special approach to the issue of economic education, paying attention to its causes and consequences. Through economic education, it is possible to develop young people as well-rounded individuals and assign them a worthy place in the world community.

In conclusion, it should be said that during the entire education, students' activities are systematically and continuously monitored. The quality of economic efficiency knowledge, skills and competences formed in the course of training in technology classes depends to a large extent on how easily they master the construction activities. For example, students can be asked to independently express their control using knowledge and skills related to the preparation of details of the item being worked on.

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